

Role of host plant resistance in successful control of brown planthopper in Central Luzon, Philippines

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Planting a single rice variety over a large area year after year may promote the breakdown of rice resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål). This cropping scenario, when combined with other factors such as overuse of insecticides, may lead to BPH outbreaks. Most farmers in Central Luzon, Philippines, have been planting for almost 10 yr the popular variety IR64. Despite this situation, BPH populations in Central Luzon are extremely low. We conducted life table studies and seedbox resistance tests on four BPH populations from Central Luzon to determine if IR64 is still resistant to BPH in Central Luzon, in the process determining the extent to which host plant resistance is responsible for low and stable BPH populations in that region.

We collected BPH in Oct 1994 from four sites, 5-50 km apart, and took the insects to IRRI to evaluate on four varieties: IR22 (no genes for BPH resistance), IR36 (*bph2* gene), IR64 (*Bph1* gene plus additional

minor gene(s)), and IR72 (*Bph3* gene).

Initially, we studied the data by analysis of variance using PROC GLM (general linear model) of the Statistical Analysis Software package, with site as a random effect. Two variables (developmental time and nymphal survival) showed a significant site-by-variety interaction; hence, means were not averaged across sites.

Fecundity among female BPH reared on IR22 and IR64 did not differ significantly across populations (see table).

In three populations, survival to the adult stage among BPH reared on IR22 and IR64 either did not differ significantly or survival was higher on IR64. In two populations, the developmental period of female BPH reared on IR64 was significantly longer than those reared on IR22. At three sites, IR64 had a lower damage rating than did IR22 in seedbox tests.

Results indicate that IR64 maintains a slight-to-moderate resistance to BPH populations in Central Luzon. It is possible that the minor gene(s) in IR64 contribute to a greater durability of resistance in this variety. The results also suggest that high levels of host plant resistance are not necessary for successful BPH management in areas, such as Central Luzon, where insecticide use is low and biological control is not disrupted. ■

Graphical genotypes of rice parental lines for resistance to green rice leafhopper

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Green rice leafhopper (GRLH), *Nephotettix cincticeps*, infects rice by transmitting viral diseases such as dwarf disease. Screening for resistance to GRLH has been conducted in Japan since the mid-1960s. The degree of resistance to GRLH was found to differ considerably among several indica varieties, but all Japanese rice varieties were susceptible (Ishii et al 1969). GRLH resistance was introduced from indica donors into japonica backgrounds. Norin PL5 was reported to express GRLH resistance by means of two complementary genes (Imbe and Iwasaki 1987) or by two dominant multiple genes (Takita and Nishiyama 1989). However, scientists have not yet determined chromosomal location of the resistance genes in those lines.

Restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) linkage map and RFLP markers have been developed in rice (Kurata et al 1994). Graphical genotype, as designated by Young and Tanksley (1989), is a powerful method for evaluating progeny strains generated from wide crosses.

We studied the resistance to GRLH of five parental lines using the graphical genotype method and examined which regions of the rice chromosomes remain as indica domains of those parental lines.

We used five lines (Norin PL2, Kanto PL6, Norin PL5, Norin PL6, and Aichi42) with resistance genes derived from indica varieties Pe-bi-hun, Tadukan, C203-1, Lepedumai, and Rantaj-emas 2, respectively (see table).

Total DNA was extracted from parental lines, original indica varieties, and three japonica varieties (Nipponbare, Reiho, Toyonishiki) using the cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide method. The extracted DNA was digested with four restriction enzymes (*Hind*III, *Bam*HI, *Eco*Rv, and *Bg*III) and separated by agarose gel (0.8%) electrophoresis. A nonradioactive method

Performance of BPH from Central Luzon, Philippines, on four rice varieties.^a 1994 wet season.

Population	Variety	Fecundity ^b	Development time ^c	Nymphal survival ^d	Damage rating ^e
Matingkis	IR22	623.90 ± 52.24 a	13.34 ± 0.17 a	13.00 ± 0.89 abc	9.0 ± 0 a
	IR36	574.20 ± 40.30 a	13.38 ± 0.18 a	13.38 ± 0.18 ab	7.6 ± 0.66 ab
	IR64	477.88 ± 83.81 a	13.16 ± 0.18 a	14.77 ± 0.83 a	7.0 ± 0.66 bc
	IR72	403.00 ± 52.84 b	13.63 ± 0.24 a	10.00 ± 0.93 c	5.6 ± 0.66 c
Silang	IR22	467.60 ± 36.19 a	13.06 ± 0.32 b	11.80 ± 1.03 a	9.0 ± 0 a
	IR36	482.00 ± 56.95 a	13.93 ± 0.35 ab	11.20 ± 0.83 a	6.3 ± 1.76 a
	IR64	435.20 ± 56.66 a	14.32 ± 0.45 a	13.90 ± 0.82 a	5.6 ± 1.33 a
	IR72	271.80 ± 59.76 b	14.12 ± 0.16 a	12.20 ± 1.04 a	5.6 ± 1.33 a
San Miguel	IR22	596.40 ± 55.10 a	13.84 ± 0.16 a	16.20 ± 0.80 a	8.33 ± 0.66 a
	IR36	459.90 ± 60.03 ab	13.09 ± 0.23 b	14.70 ± 0.79 ab	5.00 ± 1.54 b
	IR64	490.10 ± 59.14 a	13.52 ± 0.23 ab	13.30 ± 0.73 bc	5.00 ± 1.54 b
	IR72	321.10 ± 75.65 b	13.67 ± 0.24 a	11.30 ± 0.95 c	3.66 ± 0.66 b
Romero	IR22	357.10 ± 50.07 ab	13.12 ± 0.10 b	13.80 ± 1.04 a	9.0 ± 0 a
	IR36	398.80 ± 47.04 ab	14.59 ± 0.41 a	12.20 ± 1.04 ab	5.6 ± 0.66 b
	IR64	474.90 ± 37.11 a	14.35 ± 0.28 a	12.20 ± 0.90 ab	4.3 ± 0.66 bc
	IR72	317.60 ± 66.29 b	14.50 ± 0.14 a	9.80 ± 1.22 b	3.0 ± 0 c

^aMean±SE. Within a column and site, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P>0.05$) by LSD statistical test. ^bNumber of eggs laid per female, $n = 10$. ^cDays for completion of female development, $n=10$. ^dNumber of nymphs reaching adult stage (out of 20 nymphs female⁻¹). $n = 10$ females. ^e0-9 scale of the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.